

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

PROJECT ACRONYM: RECAP

PROJECT NUMBER: 693171

PROJECT FULL TITLE: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

WP1 Project Management

DELIVERABLE NUMBER & NAME:

D1.9 Report on Advisory Board meetings (4)

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

Grant Agreement Number: 693171

Acronym: RECAP

Project Full Title: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

Start Date: 01/05/2016

Duration: 30 months

Project URL: www.recap-h2020.eu

Deliverable Number & Name: D1.9: Report on Advisory Board meetings (4)

Work Package Number & Name: WP1 – Project Management

Date of Delivery: 31/10/2018

Contractual: 31/10/2018

Actual: 31/10/2018

Nature: R-Report

Dissemination Level: Public

Lead Beneficiary: 1- DRAXIS

Responsible Author: Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS), Polimachi Simeonidou (DRAXIS)

Contributions from: Alberto Lafarga (INTIA)

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

Versions	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
v1.0	22/10/2018	1	Draft version of the deliverable	DRAXIS
v2.0	30/10/2018	2	Feedback from review	INTIA
v3.0	31/10/2018	3	Final version	DRAXIS

© RECAP Consortium, 2016

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

1. Executive summary	4
2. Update of the AB list	5
3. RECAP Webinar: Solutions and results	7
4. List of AB members	9

1. Executive summary

The current deliverable is the final Report on Advisory Board (AB) meetings. The first deliverable (D1.2) was submitted on M6 and included the selection of four AB members. The second deliverable (D1.7) was submitted on M14 and reported the incorporation of two more AB members. The third deliverable (D1.8) was submitted on M23 and introduced two new members of the RECAP AB and outlined the most essential points discussed during the meetings. The current report presents the introduction of a new AB member and the outcome of the webinar conducted with the AB members.

The new AB member were initially approached via emails by means of formal invitation to participate on the AB. The AB member was informed in advance about the project's scope, status and progress through informative material that was sent via emails and he was asked for their availability for an interview. The interview of the AB member was conducted through phone. This deliverable sums up and presents the main points of the interview.

Regarding the structure of the current deliverable, Chapter 2 presents the changes made on the board from M23 to M30 and the Chapter 3 describes the webinar that was conducted among the partner and the AB members. Furthermore, it is presented the meeting held between the new AB member and the RECAP partners and finally, some of the most important recommendations of the new AB member to RECAP and how these recommendations were handled. Chapter 4 briefly presents the final members of the AB.

Since this is the final report of the AB, the RECAP consortium would like to express its gratitude for their involvement, guidance and valuable feedback at every step of the project's implementation.

2. Update of the AB list

The AB list may be updated throughout the duration of the project in a case an additional need for consultation or any major challenge will occur. Hence, a webinar will be scheduled with all the AB members aiming to inform them about the progress of the project and consult them with regards to major challenges that may occur during the pilot implementation phase.

The RECAP AB is enhanced with 1 more member and a short description of his qualifications is presented below:

Traianos Terzis

Traianos Terzis holds a bachelor degree from the Department of Plant Production of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece. He has more than 20 years of experience in AgriFood domain and the latest 10 years, he is the head manager of the plant production department of A.C of Pella.

The full list of the AB members can be found in Chapter 6, while short CVs of all members are also provided in the [RECAP platform](#).

The scope of the AB meeting was to inform AB member about the RECAP project and the challenges the consortium faces, and to offer the RECAP consortium to elicit some initial crucial recommendations for the project's implementation. Prior to the AB meeting, demo credentials were provided to Traianos in order to explore the platform and get a holistic view of it with regards to agricultural consultants and farmers' functionalities.

The meeting was held between Traianos and Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS) face-to-face at DRAXIS premises in Thessaloniki.

The meeting was held on 24th of May 2018 and it lasted for approximately 1 hour. At first, Ifigeneia welcomed Traianos on board and thanked him for his participation on the AB. Following a brief presentation of the RECAP project, highlighting the objectives and the main components of the envisioned platform, more focus was placed on the view of agricultural consultants and farmers' needs and how these needs were addressed with the RECAP platform. Furthermore, Traianos recommended some enhancement for the RECAP platform in order to deliver the maximum value both to farmers and the agricultural consultants.

Recommendations	RECAP actions
The users (farmers & consultants) should be able not only to draw the parcels' boundaries within the RECAP platform, but also to upload .shp files.	The RECAP development team has added both the functionality of drawing and upload .shp files. Furthermore, through the API, RECAP can be integrated with

	existing systems and retrieve all the needed information.
<p>The majority of the users would be agricultural consultants since few farmers handle by themselves their declarations. RECAP should pay attention both to farmers and agricultural consultants' needs.</p>	<p>On the one hand, the RECAP platform offers the same functionalities to both target groups in a simple, easy and understandable way. On the other hand, the RECAP consortium disseminated and demonstrated the RECAP functionalities through demos and manuals to all target groups in order to alleviate any operational obstacle.</p>

3. RECAP Webinar: Solutions and results

Within the last year, the RECAP solutions were integrated and pilot tested in 5 countries (Spain, Greece, Lithuania, Serbia and UK) by its end users (Paying Agencies, Farmers, Agricultural Consultants & Advisors), providing first hand results and experiences on the potential benefits of the solutions developed. Reaching the end of the project, the RECAP consortium invited the AB members to join a webinar focused at:

- Presenting the overall RECAP platform and solutions functionalities;
- Presenting the results and experiences from the pilots' implementation;
- Discussing with the AB members the RECAP platform and services within different stakeholders' groups (PAs; Farmers organisations; Extension services; Agricultural consultants; policy makers; etc.).

The meeting was held among the AB members (Alan Matthews, Prodromos Kalaitzis, Umberto Di Pasquo and Traianos Terzis) and the RECAP partners (Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia – DRAXIS, Dimitrios Petalios - CREVIS, Jason Beedell – S&P, Edward Hutley – S&P, Natalia Bellostas – INTIA, Gintare Kucinskiene – LAAS, Maja Budimir – INO, Aušrinė Matickaitė – NMA, Salomeja Rybokiene – NMA, Vassilis Sitokonstantinou – NOA and Kostas Kountouris OPEKEPE) via WebEx.

The meeting was held on 23rd of October 2018 and it lasted for approximately 2 hours. Firstly, Ifigeneia welcomed the participants and thanked them for joining the webinar. A brief introduction of the project's progress was presented to the participants from Ifigeneia. In addition, Ifigeneia demonstrated the RECAP platform and afterwards Vassilis presented the Remote Sensing Component. Lessons learnt throughout the 30 months of implementation were presented by Dimitris and the pilot partners briefly stated the outcomes derived from their cases.

A few questions were posed by the AB members. Alan asked how intensive is the work to keep the RECAP application updated since the rules differ between the areas. Ifigeneia said that from the technical perspective, no much effort is needed. The platform has been developed in such a way in order for the user to update the content in an easy way. With regards to the remote sensing, Vassilis said that for the remote sensing component there are no difference on how to handle the rules, but there are differences regarding the area, such as area's particularities, differences on the crop types and how they are defined. Consequently, slightly adaptations will be needed in order to achieve high accuracy since the remote sensing component has been designed in a scalable and transferable way.

Below there are the questions raised to the AB members by the RECAP consortium alongside with the respective responses.

1. **Do you believe that the RECAP platform is able to build bridges between the PA and farmers and improve transparency?**

Traianos Terzis: "I strongly believe that this gap will be alleviated. The farmers will be more secure that their declarations are handled with credibility since the RECAP platform offers transparency. Moreover, PA will have a better overview of the farmers that do not declare the correct crop. Consequently, the farmers will be more careful with their declarations."

Prodromos Kalaitzis: "RECAP constitutes a useful tool in the hands of concerned stakeholders to facilitate and make more transparent the process of aid distribution, provided that more implementation (technical) support will be provided also in the near future."

Alan Matthews: "This question looks at the app from the farmer's perspective. Farmers (or their agents) will already be using the official online app to submit their information to the PA. A useful feature of the app from a farmer's view is likely to be the reminders on cross-compliance activities (I don't see that the remote sensing

is relevant as the farmer will already know what crops he or she has planted). I suppose that the farmer can already correct incorrect information on the PA files using the official app. The fact that RECAP can be accessed easily on other platforms (smart phone, tablet) would make it more convenient to use for this purpose. But this assumes that the information the PA has on file is uploaded on to the RECAP app. Close integration between PA and RECAP would seem to be essential prerequisite for widespread take up.”

2. What actions should be undertaken in order to further exploit RECAP after the end of the project?

Traianos Terzis: “RECAP platform should be integrated in a real workflow with existing systems and used in a daily basis. In such a way, the added value of the RECAP solution will be highlighted and more stakeholders will be interested in adopting it.”

Prodromos Kalaitzis: “Therefore, upon completion of the project, it should be actively disseminated among stakeholders, targeting in particular farmer organisations.”

Alan Matthews: “Following on from last point, the value of RECAP would seem to be greatly enhanced where it is officially adopted by a PA who feed it with information and keep it updated. Thus, I would have thought trying to interest PAs in taking ‘ownership’ of the app and continuing to develop it would seem an important step.”

3. Do you consider that the RECAP platform can be used and/or provide services to other stakeholder within the agricultural sector i.e. policy makers, farmers cooperatives, etc, further to its main beneficiaries (Farmers, Paying Agencies, agricultural Consultants and Extension services). If yes, please provide us with a brief explanation.

Traianos Terzis: “RECAP solution might be useful in the agricultural supply chain. If RECAP would be used as a global system, then agricultural consultants would be able to have a clear overview of what is exactly cultivated in their area of interest and they would be able to adapt their workflow and policy accordingly.”

Prodromos Kalaitzis: “As per the aforementioned point, I would underline the importance of focusing on the most vulnerable stockholders (such as in countries with weak institutional and weak support structures), to disseminate and demonstrate the implementation of RECAP.”

Alan Matthews: “Integrating data from various sources has great potential to yield useful insights using big data analytical techniques, although I have difficulty in trying to give a specific example. A key requirement would seem to be that apps ‘speak’ to each other so that information can be exchanged, that farmer knows exactly who has access to his or her information and is easily able to give or retract permissions, and that information only needs to be inputted once by the farmer, not multiple times on multiple apps.”

4. List of AB members

Current Advisory Board members

Name	Organisation & Expertise
Prodromos Kalaitzis	Policy consultant in projects on the development of agri-food business and institutional structures
Peter Fane	Principal Consultant at Eurinco, European policy consultants, Agriculture, Rural development and renewable energy
Socrates Socratous	Senior Officer at the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	Director of Research, at the FORTH, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas
Clement Atzberger	Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information (IVFL), BOKU University in Vienna, Austria
Alan Matthews	Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland
Umberto Di Pasquo	Senior Policy Advisor at Copa Cogeca, the association of European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives
Alexandre Morin	Manager of the Chamber of the Chamber of Agriculture in European partnerships and projects
Traianos Terzis	Head manager of the plant production department of A.C of Pella.